

HEad and neCK TumOR (HECKTOR) Lesion Segmentation, Staging and Prognosis using Multimodal Data : Structured description of the challenge design

CHALLENGE ORGANIZATION

Title

Use the title to convey the essential information on the challenge mission.

HEad and neCK TumOR (HECKTOR) Lesion Segmentation, Staging and Prognosis using Multimodal Data

Challenge acronym

Preferable, provide a short acronym of the challenge (if any).

HECKTOR 2026

Challenge abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Head and neck (H&N;) malignancies constitute a major oncological burden globally, ranking seventh in terms of incidence and occurring more frequently in men and older individuals (Barsouk et al. 2023). The combination of radiotherapy and cetuximab is currently regarded as a standard therapeutic approach (Bonner et al. 2010). Nevertheless, disease control at the primary and regional sites remains problematic, with locoregional relapse reported in up to 40% of patients within two years of treatment completion (Chajon et al. 2013). To address this, recent work has explored radiomics approaches using positron emission tomography (PET) and computed tomography (CT) to non-invasively stratify patients according to prognosis, relying on imaging data routinely acquired for diagnosis and radiotherapy planning (Vallières et al. 2017; Bogowicz et al. 2017; Castelli et al. 2017). PET and CT capture distinct yet complementary aspects of tumor biology, metabolic activity and anatomical structure, respectively, providing synergistic information for lesion delineation and for characterizing tumor features that may be predictive of clinical outcomes, beyond conventional clinical covariates such as age, sex, and treatment type. To effectively exploit these rich data sources, advanced image analysis techniques, including radiomics as well as machine and deep learning methods, need to be carefully designed and, crucially, robustly assessed. While initial findings are encouraging, most studies to date have been conducted on limited patient cohorts, underscoring the necessity for validation on larger, multi-institutional datasets to maintain a suitable balance between feature dimensionality and sample size and to mitigate the risk of overly optimistic generalization estimates.

The HECKTOR initiative was first launched in 2020 as a benchmarking platform aimed at advancing automatic 3D bi-modal PET/CT segmentation methods for head and neck oncology, with a specific focus on delineating primary

tumors (GTVp). The following year, the challenge evolved to include a substantially larger and more diverse cohort by incorporating data from an additional clinical institution, bringing the total number of cases to 325. In parallel, a new objective was introduced: the prediction of progression-free survival (PFS), formulated as a second task with two variants depending on the availability of reference tumor contours.

In 2022, the challenge underwent a major expansion in both scale and technical difficulty. Participants were required to perform fully automatic segmentation without the aid of predefined bounding boxes, and to additionally segment metastatic lymph nodes (GTVn) alongside the primary tumor. The dataset was further enriched with contributions from three new centers, resulting in 883 and 828 cases for the segmentation and survival prediction tasks, respectively. To guarantee a strictly independent evaluation, all test cases from the 2021 edition were reassigned to the 2022 training set, and recurrence-free survival (RFS) replaced PFS as the clinical endpoint of interest.

The most recent iteration, in 2025, extended the scope once again by introducing HPV status prediction as a third task and further enlarging the cohort. Approximately 300 new cases from two additional centers were added, together with new data modalities, including radiotherapy dose distributions and treatment planning information. While tumor and lymph-node delineation and outcome prediction remained core components of the challenge, the segmentation evaluation protocol was refined to reflect these expanded objectives and increased clinical realism.

For the 2026 edition, we propose the following updates and additions to improve the clinical relevance, increase the interest of competitors, and add novelty:

1) All data included in the 2025 edition will be used (around 1200 patients) and will be updated to reach 1423 patient cases. The updates include: 1) annotation of the primary tumor and lymph nodes of around 270 cases from the Centre Hospitalier Universitaire de Brest (CHUB) center and 2) annotation of the radiological TN staging of the current missing data, 3) previously filtered public data from the existing centers (96 cases), 4) additional data from at least 3 medical centers in the UAE (around 150 cases).

2) There will be one task dedicated to deploying a pipeline encompassing a large spectrum of head and neck cancer patients' management. The end-to-end pipeline starts with segmentation, then TN staging, followed by prognosis. This framework aims to examine the model's ability to accumulate knowledge in a way that mimics the process followed by clinicians and radiologists as much as possible.

Participants may submit either modular approaches (separately optimized components) or a single end-to-end model. However, we encourage end-to-end solutions, as they more closely reflect real-world clinical scenarios and offer improved computational efficiency by reducing redundancy across intermediate steps.

3) The unified single task is closely aligned with this year's MICCAI theme of clinical translation. The goal is to promote the development of unified models that can handle all steps of clinical workflow segmentation, staging, and prognosis, similar to how a radiologist would approach a case. These subtasks are inherently interdependent, and this unified design naturally mirrors their clinical linkage, reinforcing the coherence of the overall challenge structure. This design reflects a more realistic and cost-effective path for clinical deployment, where maintaining and deploying a single model is more feasible than three separate ones.

4) Although segmentation and prognosis were available in previous editions, this edition will explore them from different perspectives. On the other hand, TN staging classification is a new task and poses a major clinical significance in the diagnosis, treatment, and prognosis of head and neck cancer patients.

5) The segmentation task will be the same as in 2025, but the evaluation will be refined to better reflect the accuracy of segmenting the lymph nodes.

Challenge keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the challenge.

Head and Neck cancer; automatic segmentation; radiomics; PET/CT; multimodal, outcome prediction.

Year

2026

Novelty of the challenge

Briefly describe the novelty of the challenge.

This challenge introduces a single, unified end-to-end pipeline that jointly addresses segmentation, TN staging, and prognosis for head and neck cancer patients. Unlike prior editions where tasks were treated independently, this framework allows modeling the dependency between tasks. As a result, segmentation is no longer an isolated objective but a clinically consequential step whose errors can propagate downstream, reflecting real-world clinical decision-making. While all three purposes (segmentation, staging, and prognosis) are mandatory due to their clinical relevance, participants will be given flexibility of using the inputs and outputs according to their preferences. This will also link to MICCAI 2026 theme for clinical translation.

A key novelty lies in encouraging participants to optimize performance across all stages simultaneously, rather than maximizing individual task metrics in isolation. This creates a fundamentally different challenge setting, where participants must design methods that balance detection accuracy, staging consistency, and prognostic relevance. By aligning the computational pipeline with the clinical workflow followed by radiologists and oncologists, the challenge emphasizes clinically meaningful modeling choices and highlights the trade-offs inherent in multi-stage decision processes that ultimately impact patient management and outcome prediction.

Task description and application scenarios

Briefly describe the application scenarios for the tasks in the challenge.

The challenge consists of a single task defined as a multi-stage assessment pipeline for head and neck cancer patients. Using multimodal FDG PET, CT, and clinical data, participating methods are required to perform automated tumor and lymph node segmentation, infer radiological TN staging, and predict recurrence-free survival. The pipeline is designed to evaluate the model's ability to accumulate and propagate information across stages, mirroring how clinicians integrate imaging findings, staging, and treatment-related factors when assessing patients.

While segmentation and prognosis tasks were present in earlier editions, this challenge revisits them from a new perspective by refining segmentation evaluation to better capture multi-lesion detection performance, and by introducing TN staging as a new, clinically central task. The resulting framework supports application scenarios such as treatment planning, risk stratification, and outcome prediction, reinforcing the clinical relevance of jointly modeling anatomy, stage, and prognosis.

FURTHER INFORMATION FOR CONFERENCE ORGANIZERS

Workshop

If the challenge is part of a workshop, please indicate the workshop.

N/A

Duration

How long does the challenge take?

2 Hours

In case you selected half or full day, please explain why you need a long slot for your challenge.

Each team will present their method and results followed by a Q&A.; There will be keynote talks.

Expected number of participants

Please explain the basis of your estimate (e.g. numbers from previous challenges) and/or provide a list of potential participants and indicate if they have already confirmed their willingness to contribute.

Based on previous years' participation (17 teams in 2020, 32 teams in 2021, and 38 in 2022, and 30 in 2025 submitting results), we can reasonably expect 30-40 teams.

Publication and future plans

Please indicate if you plan to coordinate a publication of the challenge results.

We plan to coordinate a publication (overview paper) describing the challenge results. A journal paper will be submitted to MedIA or TMI summarizing the results and outcomes of the challenge and carrying out several post-challenge analyses, such as for example low data regime evaluations, sub-cohorts analyses, etc.

MICCAI LNCS proceedings

Indicate if you want to offer MICCAI Springer LNCS proceedings to the participants. Publishing a proceedings volume is optional and at the discretion of each challenge's organizers. At a minimum, organizers must ensure that a description of each participant's submission is publicly available. Organizers who wish to publish MICCAI Springer LNCS proceedings must adhere to the MICCAI Satellite events publication process.

Yes

Collaboration with European Society of Radiology (ESR)

In collaboration with European Society of Radiology (ESR), we announce special clinical interest topics with associated clinicians who can help with the preparation of the proposals; the best 3 challenge proposals on these topics will get the opportunity to present their challenges at the European Congress of Radiology (ECR) 2027 in a special session. If you want to organize a challenge in collaboration with ESR on one of these topics, please reach out to the MICCAI Challenges Team (miccai-challenges-2026@dkfz-heidelberg.de) and we will put you in contact with the corresponding clinician.

Challenge in collaboration with ESR. Ticking 'Yes' implies that the challenge has been prepared in collaboration with the clinical contact point.

No

Space and hardware requirements

Organizers of on-site challenges must provide a fair computing environment for all participants. For instance, algorithms should run on the same computing platform provided to all.

The platform used for the online challenge will be Grand Challenge (<https://grand-challenge.org/>).

Standard equipment for presentations will be needed: projector, computer, loudspeakers and microphones.

TASK 1: Task: End-to-end pipeline of segmentation, TN staging, and prognosis

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Provide a fully automated, end-to-end prediction pipeline for head and neck cancer management using multimodal FDG PET, CT, and clinical data. The framework follows a staged clinical workflow, where outputs from earlier steps are explicitly reused in subsequent tasks. First, the task includes performing automated detection and segmentation of the primary tumor and lymph nodes. These delineations are used to extract imaging-derived features and infer the TN stage, formulated as a multi-label and multi-class classification problem. The predicted TN stage is then combined with the original multimodal inputs to predict recurrence-free survival (prognosis step). This sequential formulation reflects real-world clinical decision-making, enforces forward information flow, and enables each task to benefit from the results of preceding stages. The evaluation would depend on the metrics of each subtask: dice for primary tumor and lymph nodes segmentation, recall and balanced accuracy for TN staging, and C-index for prognosis.

The challenge consists of one main task only that includes dependent subtasks, allowing the model(s) to accumulate and build clinical knowledge. All participants enrolled should perform all three steps in the pipeline.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

Detection, segmentation, PET/CT, deep learning, radiomics, staging, outcome prediction

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Shahad Hardan - Mohamed Bin Zayed University of Artificial Intelligence, Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates

Numan Saeed - Mohamed Bin Zayed University of Artificial Intelligence, Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates

Salma Hassan - Mohamed Bin Zayed University of Artificial Intelligence, Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates

Roba Al Majzoub - Mohamed Bin Zayed University of Artificial Intelligence, Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates

Tausifa Jan Saleem - Mohamed Bin Zayed University of Artificial Intelligence, Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates

Asif Hanif- Mohamed Bin Zayed University of Artificial Intelligence, Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates

Mashrafi Monon - Mohamed Bin Zayed University of Artificial Intelligence, Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates

Mohammad Yaqub - Mohamed Bin Zayed University of Artificial Intelligence, Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates

Abhinav Jha - Washington University in St. Louis, USA and SNMMI

Arman Rahmim - BC Cancer Research Institute, Vancouver, Canada

Adrien Depeursinge - Institute of Information Systems, University of Applied Sciences Western Switzerland

(HES-SO), Sierre, Switzerland and CHUV

Vincent Andrearczyk - Institute of Information Systems, University of Applied Sciences Western Switzerland

(HES-SO), Sierre, Switzerland

Mathieu Hatt - LaTIM, INSERM, UMR 1101, Univ Brest, Brest, France

Martin Vallieres - Department of Computer Science, Université de Sherbrooke, Sherbrooke, Canada

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Shahad Hardan: shahad.hardan@mbzuai.ac.ae

Numan Saeed: numan.saeed@mbzuai.ac.ae

Salma Hassan: salma.hassan@mbzuai.ac.ae

Roba Al Majzoub: roba.majzoub@mbzuai.ac.ae

Tausifa Jan Saleem: tausifa.saleem@mbzuai.ac.ae

Asif Hanif: Asif.Hanif@mbzuai.ac.ae

Mashrafi Monon: mashrafi.monon@mbzuai.ac.ae

c) Indicate whether clinicians are part of the organizing team. If yes, describe their role.

Yes. Clinicians are part of the organizing team to 1) advise on the clinical relevance of the problem, 2) validate the evaluation criteria, and 3) annotate cases of missing TN staging and missing segmentation masks of primary tumor and lymph nodes.

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

Challenge associated with MICCAI 2026

b) Report the platform used to run the challenge.

grand-challenge.org

c) Do you agree that the your submission is shared with the platform (e.g., grand-challenge, synapse...) that you indicated?

Please note: 1) this purpose of such sharing is that the challenge chairs and the platform can communicate smoothly, your answer won't impact the review of your proposal; 2) regardless of your response to this question, it is your

responsibility to perform all actions required by the platform (e.g. filling their submission request).

Yes

d) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

2026 edition will be updated later on Grand Challenge (2025 edition is <https://hecktor25.grand-challenge.org/>)

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed. This includes the policy regarding any curation, (pre-)processing and (pre-)training steps.

Algorithms producing a fully automatic end-to-end assessment of head and neck cancer patients will be assessed. The pipeline must automatically detect and delineate the primary tumors and lymph nodes of the test cases and use these results as input for subsequent TN staging and prognosis prediction, reflecting a single integrated clinical workflow.

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or may also include publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets. Clarify whether such additional data needs to be publicly available at the time of the challenge launch. Clarify whether adding (private) annotations of the public data is allowed.

Participants can use the training data in any way they wish for training the models. Participants may use additional public data to extend the provided dataset for training the algorithm, but the use of private data (e.g., from their own institutions) is strictly prohibited. This policy ensures a fair comparison among all participating methods. However, participants may use both public and private data for scientific publication purposes, provided they explicitly disclose this in their submitted manuscripts and include results obtained using only the provided HECKTOR2026 data to highlight any potential differences.

The use of additional (public or not) data for training is permitted at the express condition that challengers acknowledge and describe the use of additional data. Participants using additional data will not be eligible for the prize. We will split the evaluation and report all results on the website and in the publications.

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but not eligible for awards and not listed in leaderboard

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

Award for the best ranked team, conditioned on a paper submission reporting the details of the methods. In the event that teams achieve identical metric scores or statistical analysis reveals no significant performance differences between top-ranking teams, we will equitably divide the awards among those teams. This approach ensures fairness while preserving the competitive spirit of the challenge and recognizes equivalent technical achievements.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.

- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

The results and the winner will be announced publicly.

Once participants submit their results on the test set to the challenge organizers via the challenge website, they will be considered fully vested in the challenge, so that their performance results (without identifying the participant unless permission is granted) will become part of any presentations, publications, or subsequent analyses derived from the Challenge at the discretion of the organizers.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

The participating teams are encouraged to publish their results in the LNCS proceedings of the challenge (following the MICCAI proceedings timeline and subject to acceptance). Participants can submit their results elsewhere when citing the overview paper, and (if so) no embargo will be applied.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

The model outputs (Segmentation, TN staging and Prognosis) will be submitted by the participating teams via grand-challenge.org. We will provide a link to the submission instructions.

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

The task submission is divided into 1+2 phases: sanity check, validation (Phase 1), and testing (Phase 2).

The sanity check consists of 3 images. Its purpose is to ensure that the participating teams are familiar with the Grand Challenge platform and that their dockers run without errors. All teams will make their submission to the sanity check phase and will receive feedback on their errors.

The validation phase (Phase 1) consists of about 50 images. All teams will submit 2 working dockers from the sanity check to the validation phase. The results on the validation dataset will be published on the leaderboard.

The testing phase (Phase 2) consists of about 500 images. The teams will have one submission to the testing phase. The official ranking of the teams will be based on the testing phase. We will request that each run must be specifically identified and described in the team report accompanying the submissions.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

Release of the Training Cases: 15th April 2026

Validation Submission: 15th June to 8th July 2026

Testing Submission: opens July 15th 2026, closes July 25th 2026

Final Report Submission: Aug. 8th 2026

Announcement of the Top 5 Teams: Aug. 20th 2026

Associated Workshop Days: Either 4th or 8th Oct. 2026

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

We indicate the answers for the cases of the different centers (list of centers is provided in 21.c).

Montreal, CA: CHUM, CHUS, HGJ, HMR (train): The ethics approval was granted by the Research Ethics Committee of McGill University Health Center (Protocol Number: MM-JGH-CR15-50).

Lausanne, CH: CHUV (train): The ethics approval was obtained from the Commission cantonale (VD) d'éthique de la recherche sur l'être humain (CER-VD) with protocol number: 2018-01513.

Poitiers, FR: CHUP (train): The fully anonymized data originates from patients who consent to the use of their data for research purposes.

Houston: MDA (train): The ethics approval was obtained from the University of Texas MD Anderson Cancer Center Institutional Review Board with protocol number: RCR03-0800.

Zürich, CH, USZ (train): The ethics approval was related to the clinical trial NCT01435252 entitled "A Phase II Study In Patients With Advanced Head And Neck Cancer Of Standard Chemoradiation And Add-On Cetuximab"

Rouen, FR: CHB (train): The fully anonymized data originates from patients who consent to the use of their data

for research purposes.

Brest, FR: CHUB (test): The fully anonymized data originates from patients who consent to the use of their data for research purposes.

Nantes, FR: CHUN (test): The fully anonymized data originates from patients who consent to the use of their data for research purposes.

Geneve, CH: HUG (test): The fully anonymized data originates from patients who consent to the use of their data for research purposes.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

Please note that the data license should not differ among sources. In case a license has to be changed, it has to be reported to the MICCAI challenges team and changed in the proposal.

CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

The code to produce the results and ranking will be made available on our GitHub repository. Link to the full code and documentation will be added to the challenge page (Same process was done in 2025)

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

Although the participating teams will be strongly encouraged to disclose or share their code, it will remain optional.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

No conflict of interest applies.

Only the organizers will have access to the test case ground truth (segmentation contours, TN classes, RFS outcome).

The challenge is funded by the BioMedIA Lab at the Mohamed Bin Zayed University of Artificial Intelligence and SNMMI. Additional companies will also be contacted to secure funding.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Prognosis,automated detection,delineation of lesions,classification (TN staging)

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration

- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Segmentation, Detection, Classification, Prediction, Prognosis

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

Task: Patients received for initial staging of H&N; cancer. The clinical goals are two-fold; the automatically detected and segmented lesions can be used as inputs for (i) clinical staging and disease characterization (through segmentation and staging) that determines the treatment planning in radiotherapy, (ii) further investigations to predict clinical outcomes such as recurrence-free survival (prognosis).

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

Patients with histologically proven H&N; cancer who underwent (chemo)radiotherapy treatment with curative intent.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

FDG-PET/CT scans (both functional FDG PET and low-dose CT modalities acquired with the same multimodal scanner are considered).

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

The information on image data will include clinical center, scanner information, DICOM meta-data including acquisition parameters and reconstruction algorithms.

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

The patient information will include center, age, gender, tobacco and alcohol consumption, performance status, treatment (radiotherapy only or chemoradiotherapy, HPV status, and T and N stages).

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary,

differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The data originates from FDG-PET and low-dose non-contrast-enhanced CT images (acquired with combined PET/CT scanners) of the H&N; region.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The algorithm target is the H&N; oropharyngeal cancer primary Gross Tumor Volume (GTVp) and lymph node gross tumor volume (GTVn) lesions. The subtasks that follow may not only exploit the images, but also the result(s) of the previous task(s).

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

To perform well in TN staging, the algorithms to be optimized must find highly accurate balanced accuracy of T and N staging classification. ,To perform well in prognosis, the algorithms to be optimized must correctly provide a reliable ranking of the survival times based on the individual risk scores (highest c-index value wins). ,To perform well in segmentation, the algorithms to be optimized must find highly accurate H&N; primary tumor and lymph node segmentation for PET/CT images. In 2026, we will use mean dice as a metric to assess segmentation quality.

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

The device(s) used to acquire the training and testing images are listed in the following for the different centers (list of centers is provided in 21.c).

HGJ: A hybrid PET/CT GE Discovery ST

CHUS: A hybrid PET/CT PhilipsGXL 16.

HMR: A hybrid PET/CT GE Discovery STE

CHUM: A hybrid PET/CT GE Discovery STE

CHUV: A hybrid PET/CT GE Discovery D690 TOF

CHUP: A hybrid PET/CT Siemens Biograph mCT 40 ToF.

MDA: Multiple hybrid PET/CT GE devices: Discovery HR, Discovery RX, Discovery ST, Discovery STE

USZ: Multiple hybrid PET/CT GE devices: Discovery HR, Discovery RX, Discovery STE, Discovery LS, Discovery 690

CHB: A hybrid PET/CT GE710.

CHUN: A hybrid PET/CT Siemens mCT 64 vision

CHUB: Multiple hybrid PET/CT scanner devices: Philips GEMINI, Siemens Biograph, Siemens Biograph Vision

HUG: A hybrid PET/CT Siemens Biograph 64 True Point scanner

Seha hospitals, UAE: TBC

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

HGJ:

For the PET portion of the FDG-PET/CT scan, a median of 584 MBq (range: 368-715) was injected intravenously. After a 90-min uptake period of rest, patients were imaged with the PET/CT imaging system. Imaging acquisition of the head and neck was performed using multiple bed positions with a median of 300 s (range: 180-420) per bed position. Attenuation corrected images were reconstructed using an ordered subset expectation maximization (OSEM) iterative algorithm and a span (axial mash) of 5. The FDG-PET slice thickness resolution was 3.27 mm for all patients and the median in-plane resolution was $3.52 \times 3.52 \text{ mm}^2$ (range: 3.52-4.69). For the CT portion of the FDG-PET/CT scan, an energy of 140 kVp with an exposure of 12 mAs was used. The CT slice thickness resolution was 3.75 mm and the median in-plane resolution was $0.98 \times 0.98 \text{ mm}^2$ for all patients.

CHUS:

For the PET portion of the FDG-PET/CT scan, a median of 325 MBq (range: 165-517) was injected intravenously. After a 90-min uptake period of rest, patients were imaged with the PET/CT imaging system. Imaging acquisition of the head and neck was performed using multiple bed positions with a median of 150 s (range: 120-151) per bed position. Attenuation corrected images were reconstructed using a LOR-RAMLA iterative algorithm. The FDG-PET slice thickness resolution was 4 mm and the median in-plane resolution was $4 \times 4 \text{ mm}^2$ for all patients. For the CT portion of the FDG-PET/CT scan, a median energy of 140 kVp (range: 12-140) with a median exposure of 210 mAs (range: 43-250) was used. The median CT slice thickness resolution was 3 mm (range: 2-5) and the median in-plane resolution was $1.17 \times 1.17 \text{ mm}^2$ (range: 0.68-1.17).

HMR:

For the PET portion of the FDG-PET/CT scan, a median of 475 MBq (range: 227-859) was injected intravenously. After a 90-min uptake period of rest, patients were imaged with the PET/CT imaging system. Imaging acquisition of the head and neck was performed using multiple bed positions with a median of 360 s (range: 120-360) per bed position. Attenuation corrected images were reconstructed using an ordered subset expectation maximization (OSEM) iterative algorithm and a median span (axial mash) of 5 (range: 3-5). The FDG-PET slice thickness resolution was 3.27 mm for all patients and the median in-plane resolution was 3.52×3.52 mm² (range: 3.52-5.47). For the CT portion of the FDG-PET/CT scan, a median energy of 140 kVp (range: 120-140) with a median exposure of 11 mAs (range: 5-16) was used. The CT slice thickness resolution was 3.75 mm for all patients and the median in-plane resolution was 0.98×0.98 mm² (range: 0.98-1.37).

CHUM:

For the PET portion of the FDG-PET/CT scan, a median of 315 MBq (range: 199-3182) was injected intravenously. After a 90-min uptake period of rest, patients were imaged with the PET/CT imaging system. Imaging acquisition of the head and neck was performed using multiple bed positions with a median of 300 s (range: 120-420) per bed position. Attenuation corrected images were reconstructed using an ordered subset expectation maximization (OSEM) iterative algorithm and a median span (axial mash) of 3 (range: 3-5). The median FDG-PET slice thickness resolution was 4 mm (range: 3.27-4) and the median in-plane resolution was 4×4 mm² (range: 3.52-5.47). For the CT portion of the FDG-PET/CT scan, a median energy of 120 kVp (range: 120-140) with a median exposure of 350 mAs (range: 5-350) was used. The median CT slice thickness resolution was 1.5 mm (range: 1.5-3.75) and the median in-plane resolution was 0.98×0.98 mm² (range: 0.98-1.37).

CHUV:

The patients fasted at least 4h before the injection of 4 Mbq/kg of (18F)-FDG (Flucis). Blood glucose levels were checked before the injection of (18F)-FDG. If not contra-indicated, intravenous contrast agents were administered before CT scanning. After a 60-min uptake period of rest, patients were imaged with the PET/CT imaging system. First, a CT (120 kV, 80 mA, 0.8-s rotation time, slice thickness 3.75 mm) was performed from the base of the skull to the mid-thigh. PET scanning was performed immediately after acquisition of the CT. Images were acquired from the base of the skull to the mid-thigh (3 min/bed position). PET images were reconstructed by using an ordered-subset expectation maximization iterative reconstruction (OSEM) (two iterations, 28 subsets) and an iterative fully 3D (DiscoveryST). CT data were used for attenuation calculation.

CHUP:

PET/CT acquisition began after 6 hours of fasting and 60 ± 5 min after injection of 3 MBq/kg of ^{18}F -FDG (421 ± 98 MBq, range 220-695 MBq). Non-contrast-enhanced, non-respiratory gated (free breathing) CT images were acquired for attenuation correction (120 kVp, Care Dose® current modulation system) with an in-plane resolution of 0.853×0.853 mm² and a 5 mm slice thickness. PET data were acquired using 2.5 minutes per bed position routine protocol and images were reconstructed using a CT-based attenuation correction and the OSEM-TrueX-TOF algorithm (with time-of-flight and spatial resolution modeling, 3 iterations and 21 subsets, 5 mm 3D Gaussian post-filtering, voxel size $4 \times 4 \times 4$ mm³).

MDA:

For the PET portion of the FDG-PET/CT scan, a median of 401 MBq (range: 327-266) was injected intravenously. After a 90-min uptake period of rest, patients were imaged with the PET/CT imaging system. Image acquisition of the head and neck was performed using multiple bed positions with a median of 180 s (range: 90-300) per bed position. Attenuation corrected images were reconstructed using an ordered subset expectation maximization (OSEM) iterative algorithm (2 iterations, 18-24 subsets, 5mm Gaussian filter). The median FDG-PET slice thickness was 3.27 mm (range: 2.99-5) and the median in-plane resolution was 5.46×5.46 mm² (range: 2.73×2.73 - 5.46×5.46). For the CT portion of the FDG-PET/CT scan, a median energy of 120 kVp (range: 100-140) with a median exposure of 185 mAs (range: 10-397) was used. The median CT slice thickness resolution was 3.75mm (range: 2.99-5) and the median in-plane resolution was 0.98×0.98 mm² (range: 0.48×0.48 - 2.734×2.734).

USZ:

For PET imaging, an activity of 178-513 MBq was administered intravenously 1h prior to the scan and after the measurement of blood sugar level. In the retrospective cohort, 2D or 3D iterative image reconstruction was used, whereas the images of the validation cohort were reconstructed with a 3D algorithm.

CHB:

Head and neck PET-CT images were acquired on a GE710 PET-CT device (General Electric, Milwaukee, USA), 90 minutes (± 5 min) after the injection of approximately 3 MBq/kg of FDG. PET and CT acquisition parameters were adapted to the patient's habitus with the patient in the radiotherapy treatment position with a contention mask. For the unenhanced CT portion of the FDG-PET/CT scan, an energy of 120 kVp with an exposure of 25 mAs was used. Attenuation corrected images were reconstructed using an ordered subset expectation maximization (OSEM) iterative algorithm (VPFX, 2 iterations and 23 subsets) and a span (axial mash) of 5. The FDG-PET slice

thickness resolution was 3.27 mm for all patients and the median in-plane resolution was $2.73 \times 2.73 \text{ mm}^2$. The CT slice thickness resolution was 2.5 mm and the median in-plane resolution was $0.98 \times 0.98 \text{ mm}^2$ for all patients.

CHUN:

After 6h fasting; 3MBq/kg; Acquisition 60 min post-injection; contrast agent if possible, acquisition steps adapted to patient's morphology

Siemens Biograph mCT: Data were reconstructed using the 3D ordinary Poisson ordered subset expectation maximization algorithm with point spread function recovery and time-of-flight information. The reconstruction parameters were 3 iterations, 21 subsets with a 2-mm full width at half maximum (FWHM) Gaussian post-filtering (voxel size $4 \times 4 \times 2 \text{ mm}^3$). Low-dose CT 3D was acquired for attenuation and scatter correction, with or without intravenous contrast enhancement, and automatic mA according to the patient weight.

Siemens Biograph Vision 450: Data were reconstructed using the 3D ordinary Poisson ordered subset expectation maximization algorithm with point spread function recovery and time-of-flight information. The reconstruction parameters were 4 iterations, 5 subsets with a 3-mm FWHM Gaussian post-filtering for the Biograph Vision 450 (voxel size $1.65 \times 1.65 \times 1.65 \text{ mm}^3$). Low-dose CT 3D was acquired for attenuation and scatter correction, with or without intravenous contrast enhancement, and automatic mA according to the patient weight.

CHUB:

For the CHUB center, PET/CT data were acquired using multiple PET/CT systems, including the Philips Gemini G-XL 6, Siemens Biograph mCT, and Siemens Biograph Vision 600, reflecting heterogeneity in scanner hardware. The administered PET dose was weight-based, approximately 6 or 3 MBq/kg, with an uptake time of 60 minutes. Several acquisition parameters were variable across cases, including PET acquisition time per position, indicating center-specific or protocol-dependent differences. PET images were reconstructed with multiple slice thicknesses (4 mm, 2 mm, and 1.6 mm) and corresponding in-plane resolutions ($4 \times 4 \text{ mm}^2$, $4 \times 4 \text{ mm}^2$, and $1.6 \times 1.6 \text{ mm}^2$), leading to notable variability in spatial resolution. CT acquisitions were performed at 120 kVp, with CT slice thicknesses of 4.0 mm, 3.0 mm, and 2.0 mm. Overall, CHUB data exhibit substantial intra-center variability in both PET and CT imaging properties, which should be considered when modeling, harmonizing, or comparing imaging-derived features across centers.

HUG:

After fasting for 6h, all patients had a single $[^{18}\text{F}]\text{FDG}$ injection, followed by a PET/MRI and a subsequent PET/CT scan. A mean dose of $373 \pm 28 \text{ MBq}$ $[^{18}\text{F}]\text{FDG}$ was injected intravenously to all patients before the PET/MRI

examination was started. During the time necessary for radiotracer uptake, a dedicated MRI of the HN region (T2-weighted, diffusion-weighted and T1-weighted sequences before and after iv. administration of a gadolinium-based contrast material), followed by total body MRI sequences was performed. The total body MRI sequences (see below) were used for attenuation correction, lesion detection, anatomic localization and lesion characterization. Afterward, a whole-body PET was acquired on the PET/MRI system. The patient was then transferred to the PET/CT scanner, and no additional [18F]FDG was injected. PET/CT images were acquired on a Biograph 64 True Point scanner (Siemens Healthcare, Erlangen, Germany). The standard dose CT scan used for attenuation correction and diagnosis (with soft tissue, bone and lung windows) had the following parameters: 120kVp, 180mAs, pitch = 1.2, collimation = 24×1.5 , 1 s per rotation, reconstructed CT slice thickness = 2 mm, reconstruction interval = 1.5 mm. PET data acquisition was started 120 ± 21 min after injection of [18F]FDG with a total of 8–9 bed positions. The delay between the end of the PET acquisition on the PET/MRI machine and the start of the PET acquisition on the PET/CT machine was on average 26 min. No iodine-based iv. contrast material was administered because: (1) according to the ESUR guidelines, for patients with a normal or moderately reduced GFR, there should be ≥ 4 h between injections of gadolinium- and iodine-based contrast agents [25]; (2) current guidelines for PET/CT do not recommend the routine use of iv. iodine-based contrast in all PET/CT examinations. The AWOSEM iterative reconstruction algorithm (4 iterations, 8 subsets, voxel size = $4 \times 4 \times 5$ mm³) was applied for PET reconstruction. Standardized uptake values (SUVs) were calculated for PET/MRI and PET/CT separately according to the standard formula.

Seha hospitals, UAE: TBC

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

HGJ: Hôpital général juif, Montréal, CA

CHUS: Centre hospitalier universitaire de Sherbrooke, Sherbrooke, CA

HMR: Hôpital Maisonneuve-Rosemont, Montréal, CA

CHUM: Centre hospitalier de l'Université de Montréal, Montréal, CA

CHUV: Centre Hospitalier Universitaire Vaudois, CH

CHUP: Centre Hospitalier Universitaire de Poitiers, FR

MDA: MD Anderson Cancer Center, Houston, Texas, USA

USZ: UniversitätsSpital Zürich, CH

CHB: Centre Henri Becquerel, Rouen, FR

CHUB: Centre Hospitalier Universitaire de Brest, FR

CHUN: Centre Hospitalier Universitaire de Nantes, FR

HUG: Hôpitaux Universitaires de Genève, CH

Seha hospitals (SSMC and Burjeel): Abu Dhabi, UAE

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

None

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

Each training and test case consists of one 3D FDG-PET volume registered to a 3D CT volume of the head and neck region, together with expert-delineated contours of the ground-truth lesions (the contours are provided only for the training cases). The segmentation labels take three values: 0 = background, 1 = primary gross tumor volume (GTVp), and 2 = nodal gross tumor volume (GTVn). If multiple lymph nodes are involved, all nodal lesions share the same label (2).

For each patient, clinical information is provided, including recruiting center, age, sex, tobacco and alcohol consumption, performance status, HPV status, and treatment (radiotherapy alone or chemoradiotherapy). Some variables may be missing for a subset of patients. For the training cases only, additional outcome variables are supplied: TN stage, recurrence flag, and recurrence-free survival. These variables, together with the annotated segmentation masks, are intended to guide model development, as both lesion segmentation, staging and prognosis prediction are expected outputs of the system. The TN staging is according to AJCC/UICC 7th Edition, the M stage will not be part of the prediction as majority of cases are M0 and most PET/CT scan are cropped to the head and neck region making detection of widespread of cancer to distant organs difficult.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

Building on the 2025 challenge, test cases that previously lacked segmentation annotations will be retrospectively annotated so they can be included in this year's edition. In total, the confirmed cohort is expected to exceed 1400 cases from at least 11 centers, including one multi-centric that includes around 3 hospitals. The training set will comprise approximately 800 cases from 7 centers. The validation set will include 50 cases from 2 centers (one already represented in the training set and one new, unseen center). The test set will consist of approximately 550

cases from 2 additional unseen centers, and we are working to acquire additional local data from multi-centric cohort with at least three hospitals in the UAE, targeting an additional 150–200 test cases to be included in the evaluation. The testing and validation data are completely new and have never been made publicly available before.

c) How much of the data are already annotated (stratified by train test in percentage)?

At present, 100% of the training and validation cases are fully annotated with ground-truth lesion segmentation masks for both GTVp and GTVn. For the test set, from the previous 2025 edition, there were 366 cases without annotation mask present; these cases are currently being annotated by expert radiologists so that the test data will also be 100% annotated for the 2026 edition.

d) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

The total sample size and the allocation into training, validation, and test sets were chosen to balance three requirements: sufficient annotated data to train high-capacity deep learning models, an independent validation subset for fair assessment and ranking of teams, and a large, truly independent multi-center test cohort to obtain robust generalization estimates.

In total, we expect to include more than 1400 cases from at least 11 centers, one of which is multicentric. Of these, approximately 800 cases (about 57%) from 7 centers are allocated to the training set. This provides several hundred fully annotated volumes, which is in line with common practice for training 3D segmentation and outcome-prediction networks and allows teams to perform internal cross-validation and ablation studies.

The validation set consists of 50 cases (about 3%) from 2 centers, one already represented in the training set, and one new, unseen center. This relatively small but sufficiently sized subset is intended solely to test participants' algorithms on data from both a known and a new center, as a first step of evaluation and ranking between teams.

The test set comprises approximately 550 cases (about 40%) from 3 unseen centers, one of which is an additional multicentric cohort with around 150–200 cases planned from at least 3 UAE hospitals. Reserving a comparatively large proportion of cases for testing is intentional: it ensures that final performance estimates are based on a diverse, multi-center cohort not seen during development, improving the precision of performance metrics and allowing meaningful subgroup analyses. Importantly, all reported numbers refer to cases with complete segmentation masks, TN staging, and RFS information, representing a substantial and clinically meaningful dataset.

e) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

The training, validation, and test cohorts are designed to reflect the real-world population of patients undergoing initial staging for oropharyngeal cancer at participating centers. We did not artificially rebalance key clinical variables; instead, the distributions of gender, HPV status, and disease stage approximate their real-world prevalence. In particular, the cohorts reflect the known epidemiology of oropharyngeal cancer, with a higher proportion of male and HPV-positive patients.

f) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

All testing and validation data are unseen and unpublished data, which are roughly 600 cases. We are also securing new data for a local multicentric cohort which will include around 3 new centers.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

Original annotations were performed differently depending on the centers.

Training set CHUM, CHUS, HGJ, HMR: Contours defining the GTVp and GTVn were drawn by an expert radiation oncologist in a radiotherapy treatment planning system. 40% (80 cases) of the training radiotherapy contours were directly drawn on the CT of the PET/CT scan and thereafter used for treatment planning. The remaining 60% (121) of the training radiotherapy contours were drawn on a different CT scan dedicated to treatment planning and were then registered to the FDG-PET/CT scan reference frame using intensity-based free-form deformable registration with the software MIM (MIM software Inc., Cleveland, OH). For the training cases, the original number of annotators is unknown.

Training set CHUP: the metabolic volume of primary tumors was automatically determined with the PET segmentation algorithm Fuzzy Locally Adaptive Bayesian (FLAB) (Hatt et al. 2009) and was then edited and corrected manually by a single expert based on the CT image, for example to correct cases where the PET-defined delineation included air or non-tumoral tissues in the corresponding CT.

Training set MDA: Contours available from radiotherapy planning were refined according to the guidelines mentioned below.

Training set USZ: The primary tumor was separately segmented in the CT and PET images. The CT segmentation was performed manually. In all cases, two radiation oncologists, both having more than 10 years of experience, were involved in the process. Contours were later post-processed for the presence of metal artifacts to exclude non-tumor related effects. If a certain tumor slice was affected by any artifacts, the entire tumor contour was erased from that slice. Tumors with more than 50% of volume not suitable for the analysis were not included in the study. Additionally, the voxels outside of soft tissue Hounsfield unit (HU) range (20 HU to 180 HU) were discarded. The tumor in the PET image was auto-segmented using a gradient-based method implemented in MIMVISTA (MIM Software Inc., Cleveland, OH).

Validation set CHB: For each patient, the GTVp and GTVn were manually drawn by using the software PET VCAR (GE Healthcare) on each FDG-PET/CT by senior nuclear medicine physicians using adaptive thresholding with visual control using merged PET and CT information.

Testing sets CHUN and CHUB: For these new testing centers, initial segmentation masks were generated using a trained deep learning model and then reviewed by a team of expert radiologists. The experts used an in-house developed annotation tool that displays the co-registered PET/CT volumes together with the model-predicted segmentation masks and provides interactive tools to edit and save the contours. All annotators followed the

same contouring guidelines and protocol as in previous challenge editions (see below) to ensure consistency with earlier datasets and to validate the quality and reliability of the final masks.

IMPORTANT: In the previous editions of the HECKTOR challenge, quality controls were performed by a board of 4 experts (certified as both radiologist and/or nuclear medicine physician) on all the datasets (training and test) to ensure consistency in ground-truth contours definition. The experts re-annotated them, when necessary, to the real tumoral volume (often smaller than volumes delineated for radiotherapy). A shared cloud environment (MIM Cloud Software Inc.) was used to centralise the contouring task and homogenize annotation software. For cases without original GTVn contours for radiotherapy, the experts annotated the cases using PET/CT fusion and N staging information. A guideline was developed by the board of experts for this quality control, reported in the following. We used a similar methodology in the 2026 edition to ensure homogeneity and quality of the contours for all centers and new data.

Guidelines for primary tumor annotation in PET/CT images:

Oropharyngeal lesions are contoured on PET/CT using information from PET and unenhanced CT acquisitions. The contouring includes the entire edges of the morphologic anomaly as depicted on unenhanced CT (mainly visualized as a mass effect) and the corresponding hypermetabolic volume, using PET acquisition, unenhanced CT and PET/CT fusion visualizations based on automatic co-registration.

The contouring excludes the hypermetabolic activity projecting outside the physical limits of the lesion (for example in the lumen of the airway or on the bony structures with no morphologic evidence of local invasion).

Standardized nomenclature per AAPM TG-263: GTVp

Special situations:

Check clinical nodal category to make sure you excluded nearby FDG-avid and/or enlarged lymph nodes (e.g. submandibular, high level II, and retropharyngeal)

In case of tonsillar fossa or base of tongue fullness/enlargement without corresponding FDG avidity, please review the clinical datasheet to rule out pre-radiation tonsillectomy or extensive biopsy. If so, this case should be excluded.

Guidelines for nodal metastases tumor annotation in PET/CT images:

Lymph nodes are contoured on PET/CT using information from PET and unenhanced CT acquisitions. The contouring includes the entire edges of the morphologic lymphadenopathy as depicted on unenhanced CT and the corresponding hypermetabolic volume, using PET acquisition, unenhanced CT and PET/CT fusion visualizations based on automatic co-registration for all cervical lymph node levels. Standardized nomenclature

for lymph node ROI: GTVn.

The contouring excludes the hypermetabolic activity projecting outside the physical limits of the lesion (for example on the bordering bony, muscular or vascular structures).

For prognosis and TN staging, the outcome ground truths for the prediction task were collected in patients' records as registered by clinicians during patient follow-ups. These include locoregional failures and distant metastases. The time $t=0$ is fixed to the date of the PET/CT scan for all centers.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

For the training and validation cases, annotators (radiologists and/or nuclear medicine physicians) were provided with a written oropharyngeal tumor segmentation protocol (see Annotation Protocol). Prior to annotation, they were instructed to delineate GTVp and GTVn on co-registered FDG-PET/CT images according to this protocol, focusing on radiologically suspicious cancer regions and applying the same inclusion/exclusion criteria used in previous editions. Annotators used an in-house annotation tool to load the PET/CT data, draw and edit 3D contours, and save the final masks.

For the new test cases, initial segmentation masks were generated by a trained segmentation model. The organizers then performed data cleaning and post-processing of these model predictions (e.g., removing obvious artefacts and non-head and neck regions) to provide a high-quality starting point, so that expert annotators refined, rather than created, contours from scratch. The same written protocol and contouring instructions as for the training and validation sets were provided to ensure consistency across all centers and data splits.

For the quality control phase in all centers, we applied the centralized guidelines and procedure detailed previously. A central reviewer, who is both a radiologist and a nuclear medicine physician, was instructed to refine the original annotations with particular emphasis on radiologically suspicious tumor regions. In addition, randomized quality checks were performed after the annotation phase, focusing on cases with the largest deviation between the model predictions and the refined ground-truth masks, to further verify and standardize the final segmentations.

No specific instructions were given for RFS value for prognosis step. The patients' outcomes were collected as recorded in the patients records at the last follow up.

TN staging values were based on pathological staging for some centers.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

The original segmentation annotators of the training and test cases were expert radiation oncologists with unknown expertise in terms of number of years of professional expertise. The annotator who performed quality

control is both an expert radiologist and nuclear medicine physician.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

A single annotation was performed per case; therefore, no merging was necessary.

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

The preprocessing involves (for both the training and test cases): (i) Computation of the Standardized Uptake Value (SUV) for the PET images (ii) Conversion of the DICOM file format to NIfTI format. The code is available on the GitHub repository: <https://github.com/voreille/hecktor>. In addition, during the preprocessing of TN staging data, nodal staging subcategories were collapsed, such that N2b and N2c were mapped to a single N2 category. This was motivated by both empirical and practical considerations. We experimentally evaluated the impact of collapsing these subcategories and observed no degradation in prognosis performance (Wiesenfarth et al., 2021), indicating that the finer-grained nodal distinctions did not provide additional predictive value for the downstream survival analysis in our dataset. Also, not all participating centers provided detailed nodal subcategory annotations. Retaining subcategories would therefore introduce inconsistent labeling across centers. Collapsing the subcategories ensures labeling uniformity and improves cross-center harmonization.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

A potential source of error comes from the lack of CT images with a contrast agent for a more accurate delineation of the primary tumor. Moreover, as the challenge evolved over years different annotators were recruited to annotate new data which may introduce some variability in ground truth annotations. However, to overcome this we have provided detailed annotation protocol to ensure unified instructions are given to the new expert radiologist to produce consistent annotation with the old version.

For prognosis, a source of error inherent to the task of survival analysis is the censored data (e.g. due to death or cessation of follow-up). The median follow-up period is approximately 40 months (5-110 months) on the training set.

TN staging labels are subject to inherent annotation uncertainty due to differences between clinical, radiological, and pathological staging, and the exact source of staging may not be uniform across cases. Clinical and imaging-based staging relies on observer interpretation and may vary across readers and institutions, with reported inter-observer disagreement typically occurring at adjacent stage boundaries (e.g., N1 vs. N2). Even pathological staging, while considered by the reference standard, is not error-free due to sampling limitations and temporal mismatch with imaging.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

None

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

For the segmentation subtask, the Dice score will be used and computed for the GTVp and GTVn classes and then averaged.

For the prognosis subtask, we use C-index as a metric.

For the TN staging subtask, and since it is a multi-label and multi-class classification problem, we use the following:

Balanced accuracy for T and N stages classification

Recall for T and N stages classification

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

Segmentation phase: Dice is well-suited for medical image segmentation because it directly measures spatial overlap between predicted and ground-truth regions and is robust to class imbalance, which is common for tumor volumes. Computing Dice separately for GTVp and GTVn ensures performance is assessed per clinically relevant target, and averaging the two provides a single, balanced summary metric without letting one class dominate the evaluation.

TN staging phase: Balanced accuracy is used to provide a balanced assessment across all TN classes, as it equally weights each stage and jointly accounts for both precision and recall, making it robust to class imbalance and adjacent-stage confusion (for example, classifying T1 instead of T2). Recall is reported alongside balanced accuracy to emphasize the model's ability to identify true disease stages, since missing a clinically relevant stage, regardless of over- or under-classification, can directly impact treatment planning and downstream prognosis.

Prognosis phase: The concordance index (C-index) quantifies the model's ability to provide an accurate ranking of the survival times based on the computed individual risk scores, generalizing the area under the ROC curve (AUC). It can account for censored data and represents the global assessment of the model discrimination power (Uno, et al. 2011).

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking. Ideally, provide the ranking scheme as a concrete pseudo code.

Since we have one overall task comprising several subtasks, performance will first be evaluated separately for each subtask:

- 1) The mean of dice scores for GTVp and GTVn for the segmentation tasks.
- 2) The mean of the balanced accuracy of the T and N stages classification.
- 3) The C-index from the prognosis task.

For each subtask, teams will be ranked according to their respective metric values. The final assessment will be based on a weighted ranking framework rather than equal weights. The weights are assigned as follows: segmentation (0.25), TN staging (0.35), and prognosis (0.40). Higher weights on TN staging and prognosis encourage participants to prioritize these tasks, while still accounting for segmentation, since degradation in segmentation propagates downstream. The elevated weight for TN staging is because of its relative underexploration in AI-based cancer research compared to segmentation. The challenge, therefore, aims to push toward more complex, clinically significant tasks and examine how TN classification influences prognosis outcomes. We have investigated the possibility of ties under this approach, and given that we have three metrics, we found that it is unlikely to lead to ties. On rare occasions that ties happen, we will depend on a consistency metric that computes the difference between the weighted average and an unweighted one, then decide on the winners accordingly.

Statistical testing, including bootstrap, will be performed later on in order to provide confidence intervals for each team's performance, allowing us to determine whether differences between top-performing teams are statistically significant.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

For the segmentation subtask, in the unlikely event of missing results on the test case, we will consider that the model predicted no GTVp nor GTVn. This imputed prediction will be used for computing the average metric.

For the TN staging subtask, in the unlikely event of missing results on the test case, it will be considered as misclassified for computing the overall balanced accuracy.

For the prognosis subtask, in the unlikely event of a missing score for one patient, all the pairs containing the missing score will be treated as non-concordant.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

For segmentation, the goal is to identify segmentation methods that perform well on both GTVn and GTVp, so a mean dice of the segmentation performance on both structures will satisfy the goal.

For TN staging, balanced accuracy serves as a generalized performance metric since it is a multi-label multi-class problem.

For prognosis, the C-index is a widely used metric for survival analysis which allows taking into account time-to-event information and censored data. (Harrell 1982) (Uno et al. 2011)

As a result, to take all subtasks into account with equal contribution, we base the ranking on a mean of all

three-subtask metrics.

Statistical analyses

Provide an overview of the statistical approaches used in the scope of the challenge analysis. Details can be provided in the parameters below. For each parameter, justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used and, if necessary, add a description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions required for the particular statistical approach.

Statistical analysis and handling of challenge results

Because the challenge is hosted on Grand Challenge, all primary evaluations and rankings will be performed automatically by the Grand Challenge platform using pre-defined metrics for segmentation, staging and prognosis prediction as outlined in the Metrics section. For each team submission, Grand Challenge will compute case-wise metrics and aggregate them across the test set (e.g. mean/median performance) and the standard deviation to derive the final leaderboard.

Assessment of variability and assumptions

The primary leaderboard on Grand Challenge is based on deterministic computation of the agreed metrics and does not rely on strong distributional assumptions. To provide an indication of variability and robustness of the rankings, the organizers will perform an additional post-hoc analysis on the test results by re-computing metrics on resampled versions of the test cohort (non-parametric bootstrap at the patient level). This yields empirical variability of team performance and gives an indication of how stable the top ranks are with respect to sampling variation in the test set, without assuming any data distribution.

Provide a description of how the precision of the performance estimates of individual algorithms is assessed (e.g. confidence interval of the mean on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap, confidence interval of the accuracy on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap).

The precision of the performance estimates for each participating algorithm will be assessed in an additional post-hoc analysis performed by the organizers, using patient-level percentile bootstrap confidence intervals on the held-out test set. For each algorithm and each primary metric, Grand Challenge will compute case-wise metric values on all test patients. These per-case metrics will be exported and used to construct bootstrap samples by repeatedly resampling patients with replacement and recomputing the aggregated metric for each resample.

The empirical distribution of the resampled metrics is then used to derive 95% percentile bootstrap confidence intervals, defined by the 2.5th and 97.5th percentiles of the bootstrap distribution. For segmentation metrics, this yields confidence intervals for the mean (or median) test-set performance; for staging and prognosis metrics, it provides corresponding confidence intervals on the test set. These intervals quantify the uncertainty due to finite test-set size and provide a measure of how precisely each algorithm's performance is estimated, while the official Grand Challenge leaderboard itself is based on the point estimates computed on the full test cohort.

Provide a description of how variability of the performance of individual algorithms across test cases is assessed (e.g. SD across test cases, IQR, graphs, reporting outliers...).

Variability of each algorithm's performance across test cases will be quantified directly from the case-wise metrics computed by the Grand Challenge platform. For every submission and every primary metric, Grand Challenge calculates the metric per test case; these values are then summarized by both the mean and the standard

deviation (SD) across all test cases. The SD provides a numerical measure of how strongly an algorithm's performance fluctuates from patient to patient.

In addition to mean \pm SD, we will inspect the full distribution of per-case metrics by exporting the case-wise results from Grand Challenge and computing further summary statistics such as the median and interquartile range (IQR), as well as generating distribution plots (e.g., boxplots or violin plots) for the top-performing methods. Outlier cases (e.g., those in the lowest tail of the metric distribution) will be identified descriptively and may be examined qualitatively to characterize typical failure modes. Together, these numerical summaries and graphical displays provide a clear picture of how stable or variable each algorithm is across the diverse test cohort.

Provide a description of how variability of rankings is assessed.

The official leaderboard provided by Grand Challenge is deterministic and based on predefined aggregated primary metrics across all test cases. Given that the challenge comprises three expected outputs and multiple metrics per output, rankings are derived from a multidimensional performance profile, making exact ties between teams unlikely in practice.

To assess the variability and stability of these rankings, the organizers will perform an additional post-hoc analysis using the per-case metrics exported from Grand Challenge. Specifically, we will apply patient-level non-parametric bootstrap resampling of the test set. For each bootstrap replicate, test cases are sampled with replacement, the aggregated performance metrics are recomputed for each algorithm, and a new ranking is derived. Repeating this procedure many times yields an empirical distribution of ranks for each algorithm.

This resampling-based assessment is distribution-free and quantifies how sensitive the observed ranking is to sampling variability in the test cohort. It complements the point-estimate leaderboard by indicating which rank differences are robust and which are potentially unstable due to finite test-set size.

Provide a description of statistical tests that are used to assess whether the differences in performance between algorithms are statistically significant.

The official Grand Challenge leaderboard is based on point estimates of the predefined metrics and does not rely on formal hypothesis testing. In addition, the organizers will perform post-hoc statistical tests to assess whether observed differences between algorithms (in particular among the top-ranked teams) are statistically significant.

Using the per-case metrics exported from Grand Challenge, we will apply paired, non-parametric tests at the patient level, since each test case is evaluated by all algorithms:

For continuous metrics, we will compare algorithms using a two-sided Wilcoxon signed-rank test or an equivalent paired permutation test based on the case-wise differences in metric values. For binary outcomes, we will use McNemar's test on paired outcome data. For other metrics, we will use a paired comparison (e.g., DeLong-type test or a permutation-based comparison) on the case-level prediction scores.

These tests make minimal assumptions (primarily that test cases are independent, and that algorithm performances can be compared on a paired basis) and avoid reliance on normality.

Provide a description of the missing data handling.

For the purpose of the challenge ranking, only cases with complete information on lesion segmentation masks, TN staging, and recurrence-free survival (RFS) are included in the test sets. Therefore, no imputation or special missing data handling is required in the evaluation pipeline. Participants will be required to submit docker container to provide predictions for all test cases; submissions with missing or invalid outputs for a case will be handled according to the standard Grand Challenge rules (e.g. treated as failed predictions for that case). Clinical data may contain missing fields as reflected in training data as well, so participants should have pre-processing pipeline in place as part of their algorithm to account for that.

Indicate any software product that is used for all data analysis methods.

All metrics used for the official ranking will be implemented within the Grand Challenge evaluation infrastructure. Any additional post-hoc statistical analysis (e.g. bootstrap summaries, plots of metric distributions) will be performed by the organizers using standard open-source tools such as Python (NumPy, SciPy, pandas, scikit-learn).

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

Similarly to 2022, an ensemble using STAPLE (Warfield, Zou, and Wells 2004) will be performed with all the predictions from the participants, as well as only the five best.

The correlation of the performance with the tumor size will be evaluated. The results will be compared across the different centers of the test set. In addition, an analysis of the location of segmentation false positives will be used to reveal if they are located in the vicinity of the primary tumor or in other regions of the oropharynx.

ADDITIONAL POINTS

References

Please include any reference important for the challenge design, for example publications on the data, the annotation process or the chosen metrics as well as DOIs referring to data or code.

Blanc-Durand, Paul, Axel Van Der Gucht, Niklaus Schaefer, Emmanuel Itti, and John O. Prior. 2018. "Automatic Lesion Detection and Segmentation of 18F-FET PET in Gliomas: A Full 3D U-Net Convolutional Neural Network Study." *PloS One* 13 (4): e0195798.

Bogowicz, Marta, Oliver Riesterer, Luisa Sabrina Stark, Gabriela Studer, Jan Unkelbach, Matthias Guckenberger, and Stephanie Tanadini-Lang. 2017. "Comparison of PET and CT Radiomics for Prediction of Local Tumor Control in Head and Neck Squamous Cell Carcinoma." *Acta Oncologica* 56 (11): 1531–36.

Bonner, James A., Paul M. Harari, Jordi Giralt, Roger B. Cohen, Christopher U. Jones, Ranjan K. Sur, David Raben, et

- al. 2010. "Radiotherapy plus Cetuximab for Locoregionally Advanced Head and Neck Cancer: 5-Year Survival Data from a Phase 3 Randomised Trial, and Relation between Cetuximab-Induced Rash and Survival." *The Lancet Oncology* 11 (1): 21–28.
- Castelli, J., A. Depeursinge, V. Ndoh, J. O. Prior, M. Ozsahin, A. Devillers, H. Bouchaab, et al. 2017. "A PET-Based Nomogram for Oropharyngeal Cancers." *European Journal of Cancer* 75 (April): 222–30.
- Chajon, Enrique, Caroline Lafond, Guillaume Louvel, Joël Castelli, Danièle Williaume, Olivier Henry, Franck Jégoux, et al. 2013. "Salivary Gland-Sparing Other than Parotid-Sparing in Definitive Head-and-Neck Intensity-Modulated Radiotherapy Does Not Seem to Jeopardize Local Control." *Radiation Oncology*.
<https://doi.org/10.1186/1748-717x-8-132>.
- Harrell, Frank E. 1982. "Evaluating the Yield of Medical Tests." *JAMA: The Journal of the American Medical Association*. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.1982.03320430047030>.
- Hatt, Mathieu, Catherine Cheze le Rest, Alexandre Turzo, Christian Roux, and Dimitris Visvikis. 2009. "A Fuzzy Locally Adaptive Bayesian Segmentation Approach for Volume Determination in PET." *IEEE Transactions on Medical Imaging* 28 (6): 881–93.
- Hatt, Mathieu, Florent Tixier, Marie-Charlotte Desseroit, Bogdan Badic, Baptiste Laurent, Dimitris Visvikis, and Catherine Cheze Le Rest. 2019. "Revisiting the Identification of Tumor Sub-Volumes Predictive of Residual Uptake after (chemo)radiotherapy: Influence of Segmentation Methods on F-FDG PET/CT Images." *Scientific Reports* 9 (1): 14925.
- Heimann, Tobias, and Hans-Peter Meinzer. 2009. "Statistical Shape Models for 3D Medical Image Segmentation: A Review." *Medical Image Analysis*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.media.2009.05.004>.
- Legot, Floriane, Florent Tixier, Minea Hadzic, Thomas Pinto-Leite, Christelle Gallais, Rémy Perdrisot, Xavier Dufour, and Catherine Cheze-Le-Rest. 2018. "Use of Baseline 18F-FDG PET Scan to Identify Initial Sub-Volumes with Local Failure after Concomitant Radio-Chemotherapy in Head and Neck Cancer." *Oncotarget* 9 (31): 21811–19.
- Menze, Bjoern H., Andras Jakab, Stefan Bauer, Jayashree Kalpathy-Cramer, Keyvan Farahani, Justin Kirby, Yuliya Burren, et al. 2015. "The Multimodal Brain Tumor Image Segmentation Benchmark (BRATS)." *IEEE Transactions on Medical Imaging* 34 (10): 1993–2024.
- Parkin, D. M., F. Bray, J. Ferlay, and P. Pisani. 2005. "Global Cancer Statistics, 2002." *CA: A Cancer Journal for Clinicians*. <https://doi.org/10.3322/canjclin.55.2.74>.
- Shiri I, Arabi H, Sanaat A, Jenabi E, Becker M, Zaidi H. Fully Automated Gross Tumor Volume Delineation From PET in Head and Neck Cancer Using Deep Learning Algorithms. *Clin Nucl Med*. 2021;46(11):872-883.
[doi:10.1097/RLU.0000000000003789](https://doi.org/10.1097/RLU.0000000000003789)
- Song, Qi, Junjie Bai, Dongfeng Han, Sudershan Bhatia, Wenqing Sun, William Rockey, John E. Bayouth, John M. Buatti, and Xiaodong Wu. 2013. "Optimal Co-Segmentation of Tumor in PET-CT Images with Context Information."

IEEE Transactions on Medical Imaging 32 (9): 1685–97.

Uno, Hajime, Tianxi Cai, Michael J. Pencina, Ralph B. D'Agostino, and L. J. Wei. 2011. "On the C-Statistics for Evaluating Overall Adequacy of Risk Prediction Procedures with Censored Survival Data." *Statistics in Medicine* 30 (10): 1105–17.

Vallières, Martin, Emily Kay-Rivest, Léo Jean Perrin, Xavier Liem, Christophe Furstoss, Hugo J. W. L. Aerts, Nader Khaouam, et al. 2017. "Radiomics Strategies for Risk Assessment of Tumour Failure in Head-and-Neck Cancer." *Scientific Reports* 7 (1): 10117.

Warfield, Simon K., Kelly H. Zou, and William M. Wells. 2004. "Simultaneous Truth and Performance Level Estimation (STAPLE): An Algorithm for the Validation of Image Segmentation." *IEEE Transactions on Medical Imaging* 23 (7): 903–21.

Grossberg A, Mohamed A, Elhalawani H, Bennett W, Smith K, Nolan T, Chamchod S, Kantor M, Browne T, Hutcheson K, Gunn G, Garden A, Frank S, Rosenthal D, Freymann J, Fuller C.(2017). Data from Head and Neck Cancer CT Atlas. The Cancer Imaging Archive. DOI: 10.7937/K9/TCIA.2017.umz8dv6s

Moe, Yngve Mardal, Aurora Rosvoll Groendahl, Martine Mulstad, Oliver Tomic, Ulf Indahl, Einar Dale, Eirik Malinen, and Cecilia Marie Futsaether. "Deep learning for automatic tumour segmentation in PET/CT images of patients with head and neck cancers." (2019).

Wee, L., & Dekker, A. (2019). Data from Head-Neck-Radiomics-HN1 [Data set]. The Cancer Imaging Archive. <https://doi.org/10.7937/tcia.2019.8kap372n>.

Andrearczyk, Vincent, Valentin Oreiller, and Adrien Depeursinge. "Oropharynx detection in PET-CT for tumor segmentation." *Irish Machine Vision and Image Processing* (2020).

Kumar, Neeraj, Ruchika Verma, Sanuj Sharma, Surabhi Bhargava, Abhishek Vahadane, and Amit Sethi. "A dataset and a technique for generalized nuclear segmentation for computational pathology." *IEEE transactions on medical imaging* 36, no. 7 (2017): 1550-1560.

Vincent Andrearczyk, Valentin Oreiller, Sarah Boughdad, Catherine Chez Le Rest, Hesham Elhalawani, Mario Jreige, John O. Prior, Martin Vallières, Dimitris Visvikis, Mathieu Hatt, Adrien Depeursinge, Overview of the HECKTOR challenge at MICCAI 2021: Automatic Head and Neck Tumor Segmentation and Outcome Prediction in PET/CT images. LNCS challenges, 2021.

Valentin Oreiller et al., Head and Neck Tumor Segmentation in PET/CT: The HECKTOR Challenge, *Medical Image Analysis*, 2021 (under revision)

Aaron Carass, Snehashis Roy, Adrian Gherman, Jacob C Reinhold, Andrew Jesson, Tal Arbel, Oskar Maier, Heinz Handels, Mohsen Ghafoorian, Bram Platel, Ariel Birenbaum, Hayit Greenspan, Dzung L Pham, Ciprian M Crainiceanu, Peter A Calabresi, Jerry L Prince, William R Gray Roncal, Russell T Shinohara, Ipek Oguz. Evaluating White Matter Lesion Segmentations with Refined Sørensen-Dice Analysis *Sci Rep* . 2020 May 19;10(1):8242. doi:

10.1038/s41598-020-64803-w.

Barsouk A, Aluru JS, Rawla P, Saginala K, Barsouk A. Epidemiology, Risk Factors, and Prevention of Head and Neck Squamous Cell Carcinoma. *Med Sci (Basel)*. 2023 Jun 13;11(2):42. doi: 10.3390/medsci11020042. PMID: 37367741; PMCID: PMC10304137.

Further comments

Further comments from the organizers.

NA